

Synthesis and anticancer evaluation of novel clubbed triazolyl indenoisoquinoline as topoisomerase I inhibitors

B. A. Baviskar^{a*}, S. S. Khadabadi^a, S. L. Deore^a and M. R. Shiradkar^b

^aGovernment College of Pharmacy, Kathora Naka, Amravati-444 604, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : bhushan_baviskar@rediffmail.com

^bDr. Reddy's Laboratories, Ameerpet, Hyderabad, India

Manuscript received online 29 January 2012, revised 12 February 2012, accepted 18 February 2012

Abstract : In continuation to our work for the development of new anticancer agents, novel clubbed triazolylindenoisoquinoline derivatives were synthesized in good yields and characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectral and elemental analyses. The prepared compounds were tested for their *in vitro* anticancer activity against 05 human cancer cell lines including human lung (HOP62), ovarian (OVKAR3), breast (ZR751), leukemia (HL60) and prostate (DU145) cancer cell lines and showed potential anticancer activity when compared with the Doxorubicin as a reference drug. The results of anticancer activity indicate that the most of synthesized compounds showed significant to weak cytotoxic effect on the different cell lines. Among the twenty-one prepared compounds, four compounds exhibited strong topoisomerase I inhibitory activity but different from that of camptothecin.

Keywords : Triazole, indenoisoquinoline, DNA topoisomerase I, inhibition, anticancer activity.

Introduction

Cancer has been seriously threatening the health and life of humans for a long period and has become the leading causes of death in the world population¹. DNA topoisomerases, regulates the relaxation/supercoiling of double-stranded DNA by transiently break one or two strands of DNA^{2,3}. DNA topoisomerase I (Top I) is nuclear enzyme plays an important role in DNA replication, transcription, and recombination^{4,5}. Topoisomerase I breaks and rejoins only one of the two strands during catalysis^{6,7} and act through transesterification of Tyr723 that breaks a single strand of the phosphodiester linkage to the DNA. After cleavage, the scissile DNA strand can rotate around the non-scissile strand and thus relaxing the double helix^{8,9}. Camptothecin (CPT), an alkaloid obtained from bark of Chinese tree *Camptotheca acuminata* was the first agent recognized as a TOP1-targeting agent¹⁰. Camptothecin derivatives¹¹⁻¹³ topotecan and irinotecan are currently used in the treatment of various cancers, however they have limitations such as poor solubility, reversibility of cleavage-complex formation, E-ring opening and dose-limiting toxicity¹⁴⁻¹⁸. The indenoisoquinolines, a class of noncamptothecin TOP1 inhibitor

was discovered as an alternative to the camptothecins¹⁹⁻²². Concerning the antitumor activity many triazole derivatives exhibit antiproliferative activity²³⁻²⁶. In view of these data, we aimed the synthesis of clubbed triazolyl indenoisoquinoline and they were evaluated for anticancer and topo I inhibitory activities, and studied for structure-activity relationships.

Results and discussion

Compounds **1**, **2**, **3**, **4**, **5**, **6**, **7**, **8a-c**, **9a-j** and **10** were synthesized using reported methods²⁷⁻³¹. Compound **1** was converted to thiocarbazate salts by treatment with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide, which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave **2**. Which, when treated with acetic anhydride for 2 h to give **3** (Scheme 1). The transformed compound **3** on treatment with diiodomethane in the presence of strong alkali, that is, potassium hydroxide gave **4** (Scheme 2). Title compound **3** was treated with chloroacetonitrile, which on neutralization with sodium carbonate gave precipitates of compounds **5** (Scheme 3). Compound **3**, when treated with methyl bromoacetate in presence of sodium acetate, produced **6**. Chemical transformation of **6** to **7** was achieved

Scheme 1. Synthesis of lead compound/s.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of bis derivatives (4).

Scheme 3. Synthesis of cyano analogs (5).

by treating it with hydrazine hydrate (Scheme 4). While compound 7, on treatment with appropriate acid chlorides, furnished 8a-c. Schiff bases, the condensation products of 9a-j, were synthesized by treating 7 with benzaldehyde and confirmed by absence of triplet of NH of

hydrazide. Compound 7 were converted to thiocarbamate salts by treatment with carbon disulfide and potassium hydroxide, which on treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave 10 (Scheme 5). The NMR spectra (Table 1) confirmed formation of triazole derivative from hydrazide,

Scheme 4. Synthesis of hydrazides (7).

Scheme 5. Synthesis of triazole-amides (8a-c), Schiff bases (9a-j) and triazolo-s-triazole (10).

which shows presence of sulfhydryl proton at δ value 13.59.

All the synthesized triazolyl-indeno[1,2-*c*]isoquinoline derivatives were evaluated *in vitro* against a panel of five cancer cell lines including human lung (HOP62), ovarian (OVKAR3), breast (ZR751), leukemia (HL60) and prostate (DU145) cancer cell lines compared with the Doxo-

rubicin (ADR) as a reference drug using SRB (Sulforhodamine B) assay. The results of the assays are reported in Table 1. The compounds were tested at a different range of concentrations to define their inhibitory activity where camptothecin was used as the standard drug for DNA topoisomerase I respectively, to compare their activities (Table 2). The supercoiled DNA was

Table 1. Spectral data of synthesized compounds

Compd.	IR (KBr, cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆) δ (ppm)	Mass (<i>m/z</i> , %)
3	3428 (NH), 2570 (SH), 2346, 1697, 1682 (C=O), 1616, 1560 (C=N), 1506, 1448 (C=C, aromatic), 1339 (C-N)	2.05 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.71 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7.1 Hz, CH ₂), 3.44 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.83 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 6.09 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.10 (1H, s, ArH), 7.18 (1H, s, ArH), 7.26 (1H, s, ArH), 7.48 (1H, s, ArH), 8.07 (1H, s, NH), 13.72 (1H, br s, SH)	536 (100, M+1)
5	3422 (NH), 1672 (C=O), 1619, 1558 (C=N), 1502, 1496, 1446 (C=C, aromatic), 1336 (C-N)	2.02 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.65 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7.4 Hz, CH ₂), 3.41 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.90 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.25 (2H, s, CH ₂), 6.04 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.19 (1H, s, ArH), 7.21 (1H, s, ArH), 7.33 (1H, s, ArH), 7.47 (1H, s, ArH), 8.00 (1H, s, NH)	-
6	3428 (NH), 1659 (C=O), 1558 (C=N), 1506, 1479, 1458, 1430, 1301, 1227 (C=C, aromatic), 1332 (C-N)	2.04 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.72 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7.6 Hz, CH ₂), 3.31 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.58 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.75 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.36 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.22 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.40 (1H, s, ArH), 7.46 (1H, s, ArH), 7.68 (1H, s, ArH), 8.00 (1H, s, NH)	-
7	3428 (-NH ₂), 3334 (-N-H), 1678 (C=O), 1610, 1554 (C=N), 1504, 1478, 1432 (C=C, aromatic), 1335 (C-N)	2.03 (2H, s, NH ₂), 2.28 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.80 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.32 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.83 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.27 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.17 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.20 (1H, s, ArH), 7.26 (1H, s, ArH), 7.28 (1H, s, ArH), 7.48 (1H, s, ArH), 8.01 (2H, s, NH)	608 (89, M+1)
8a	3176 (NH), 1730 (C=O), 1610, 1583 (C=N), 1505, 1479, 1459, 1431, 1299, 1226 (C=C, aromatic), 788 (C-S-C)	1.98 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.65 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.46 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.83 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.20 (2H, s, CH ₂), 6.21 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.27 (1H, s, ArH), 7.43 (1H, s, ArH), 7.58 (1H, s, ArH), 7.63 (1H, s, ArH), 7.83 (2H, m, ArH), 8.03 (1H, s, ArH), 8.23 (2H, m, ArH), 8.68 (3H, s, NH)	-
9a	3176 (NH), 1620 (C=O), 1583 (C=N), 1501, 1480, 1455 (C=C, aromatic), 1305 (C-N), 711 (C-S-C)	2.01 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.68 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 7.1 Hz, CH ₂), 3.18 (2H, t, CH ₂), 3.89 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.22 (2H, s, CH ₂), 5.82 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.06 (1H, s, ArH), 7.12 (1H, s, ArH), 7.38 (1H, s, ArH), 7.45 (1H, s, ArH), 7.52 (3H, m, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.83 (2H, m, ArH), 8.07 (2H, s, NH), 8.64 (1H, s, CH)	-
10	3327 (NH ₂), 3210 (NH), 2584 (SH), 1678 (C=O), 1594 (C=N), 1333 (C-N), 709 (C-S-C)	-	-

fully relaxed by the enzyme in the presence of the organic solvent, DMSO, without any inhibition of the DNA topoisomerase I activity. A thicker band of supercoiled form implies more potent inhibitory activity of the compound. Amongst the tested set of 21 compounds of derivatives (see Fig. 1), compounds **2**, **5**, **7** and **9a** potentially inhibited DNA topoisomerase I, whereas compounds

1, **3**, **4**, **8a-c**, **9b-j** were showed moderate to weak DNA topoisomerase I inhibitory activity. Compounds **6** and **10** were found to be inactive.

Experimental

Chemistry :

The melting points were recorded on electrothermal

Table 2. *In vitro* anticancer (GI50 μ M) and topoisomerase I inhibitory activities of triazolyl-indenoisoquinoline analogues

Compd.	Cytotoxicity (GI50 in μ M) ^a					top-I Cleavage ^b
	HOP62	OVKAR3	ZR751	HL60	DU145	
1	> 80	15.4	25.9	> 80	25.9	nt
2	2.5	0.9	8.7	3.26	4.3	+++
3	9.1	8.3	10.2	9.8	7.9	++
4	> 80	> 80	69.1	56.5	> 80	-
5	1.3	3.4	4.65	2.5	1.7	+++
6	35.4	> 80	> 80	75.5	> 80	-
7	8.14	3.4	6.7	1.7	5.9	+++
8a	17.9	20.5	15.49	21.3	23.5	+
8b	16.8	12.5	19.2	18.1	13.4	+
8c	17.9	26.4	25.4	16.3	28.5	+
9a	9.1	10.3	6.2	5.6	2.5	+++
9b	18.1	13.4	16.7	11.7	15.9	++
9c	39.7	56.2	32.07	30.2	65.7	-
9d	9.1	9.8	8.2	10.6	9.5	++
9e	36.8	26.4	56.2	40.8	36.7	-
9f	39.7	56.2	32.07	30.2	65.7	+
9g	23.5	11.4	15.5	10.2	16.8	+
9h	23.1	24.1	25.12	23.5	21.45	+
9i	9.5	10.6	5.49	8.26	9.5	++
9j	27.2	19.1	39.1	56	26.2	+
10	78.7	> 80	> 80	71.2	75.6	-
ADR	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	nt
CPT	2.5	1.85	2.8	3.65	9.56	++

^aThe cytotoxicity GI50 values are the concentrations corresponding to 50% growth inhibition.

^bThe compounds were tested at concentrations ranging up to 10 μ M. The activity of the compounds to produce top1-mediated DNA cleavage was expressed semiquantitatively as follows : - : very weak activity; + : weak activity; ++ : similar activity as camptothecin; +++ : greater activity than camptothecin. nt : not tested.

apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Shmandizu model IRAFFINITY-1 in KBr. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Mercury 300 MHz instrument using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent using TMS as internal standard; the chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm and coupling constants (*J*) are given in Hz. Mass spectra were recorded on a Finning LCQ mass spectrometer. Elemental analyses were performed on a Heracus CHN-Rapid Analyser. Analyses indicated by the symbols of the elements of functions were within \pm 0.4% of the theoretical values. The purity of the compounds was checked on Merck precoated silica gel 60 F-254.

Preparation of 3-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)propanohydrazidecarbodithiopotassium salt (1) and 6-[2-(4-amino-5-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)ethyl]-2,3-dimethoxy-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinoline-5,12-dione (2) :

Above titled compound were prepared as per the reported method²⁷⁻³¹.

Synthesis of N1-{3-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-5-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl}-acetamide (3) :

The triazole (2) (1 mmol) in 20 mL of DMF was treated dropwise with an equimolar amount of acetic anhydride in 15 mL DMF at 0 °C, which was stirred for 30–45 min. At the end of stirring a precipitate was observed. The precipitate was then filtered, washed thoroughly with CHCl₃ and hexanes and crystallized to provide an orange solid. Yield 68%, m.p. 280–285 °C, M.W. 535.53 (Found : C, 56.01; H, 3.98; N, 13.12. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₁N₅O₇S : C, 56.07; H, 3.95; N, 13.08%).

Synthesis of N1-(5-methylenebis{sulfanedial-3-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl})acetamide (4) :

The triazoleacetamide (3) (1 mmol), diiodomethane (1.5 mmol) and 5.6 g (1 mmol) potassium hydroxide were dissolved in 20 ml of dichloromethane in 10 ml ethanol was heated under reflux for 5 h the mixture was cooled and solid separated wash thoroughly with hexane : ethyl acetate to afford brown coloured solid. Yield : 71%, m.p. 274–276 °C, M.W. 548.55.

Synthesis of N1-{3-[(cyanomethyl)sulfanyl]-5-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl}acetamide (5) :

The triazoleacetamide (3) (1 mmol) was mixed with 1.2 ml (2 mmol) of chloroacetonitrile and dissolved in 5 ml of ethanol then add 25 ml of water. Neutralization with sodium carbonate gave a precipitate, which was filtered, washed with cold water (2 \times 20 ml), and crystallized with ethyl acetate to get off white coloured solid. Yield 65%. m.p. 218–220 °C, M.W. 574.56 (Found :

Fig. 1. Comparison showing the inhibitory effects of tested compounds and reference drug camptothecin on eukaryotic DNA topoisomerase I relaxation assay. Lane 1; Plasmid DNA [pBS (SK+)] with incubation mixture without enzyme. Lane 2; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB (control). Lane 3; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Compd. 2 (10 μ M). Lane 4; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Compd. 5 (10 μ M). Lane 5; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Compd. 6 (10 μ M). Lane 6; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Compd. 7 (10 μ M). Lane 7; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Compd. 9a (10 μ M). Lane 8; pBS(SK+)DNA + LdTOPIB + Camptothecin (positive inhibitor) at a concentration of 10 μ M.

C, 56.39; H, 3.89; N, 14.67. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{22}N_6O_7S$: C, 56.44; H, 3.86; N, 14.63%.

Synthesis of methyl 2-({4-(acetylamino)-5-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl}sulfanyl)acetate (6) :

A solution of triazoleacetamide (**3**) (1 mmol), 0.4 g (1 mmol) of sodium hydroxide and methyl bromoacetate 1.53 g (1 mmol) was prepared in 10 ml ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h. Then the mixture was cooled and poured on ice. The solid thus separated was filtered. After cooling, filtrate gave almost pure cream coloured solid product. Yield 76%, m.p. 218–220 $^{\circ}$ C, M.W. 607.59 (Found : C, 55.30; H, 4.19; N, 11.58. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{25}N_5O_9S$: C, 55.35; H, 4.15; N, 11.53%).

Synthesis of N1-[3-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-5-[(2-hydrazino-2-oxoethyl)sulfanyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]acetamide (7) :

A solution of **6** (1 mmol) with 5 ml (1 mmol) hydrazine hydrate (98%) was prepared in 10 ml ethanol. Then the mixture was refluxed for 5 h and the solution was poured onto ice cold water. The precipitate was filtered and crude product thus obtained was purified by column chromatography eluting with a gradient of chloroform/methanol : triethylamine (4 : 1), to provide a red solid.

Yield 62%, m.p. 243–246 $^{\circ}$ C, M.W. 607.59 (Found : C, 53.32; H, 4.11; N, 16.18. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{25}N_7O_8S$: C, 53.37; H, 4.15; N, 16.14%).

Synthesis of N1-[3-[2-(2-benzoylhydrazino)-2-oxoethyl)sulfanyl]-5-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]acetamide (8a) :

To a solution of **7** (1 mmol) in dichloromethane (excess amount), appropriate acid chloride (1 mmol) was added dropwise with constant vigorous stirring. After 25 min of stirring the mixture was refluxed for 5 h and the solution was poured on to ice cold water and product thus obtained crystallized from *n*-hexane-carbon tetrachloride mixture to get dark brown coloured solid. Other compounds **8b**, **8c** were obtained in similar manner. Yield 68%, m.p. 178–180 $^{\circ}$ C, M.W. 711.70 (Found : C, 57.32; H, 4.16; N, 13.85. Calcd. for $C_{34}H_{29}N_7O_9S$: C, 57.38; H, 4.11; N, 13.78%).

Synthesis of N1-[3-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-5-({2-oxo-2-[2-(phenylmethylene)hydrazino]ethyl}sulfanyl)-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]acetamide (9a) :

A solution of **7** (1 mmol) with benzaldehyde (1 mmol)

was prepared in 10 ml ethanol. Add 4 drops of glacial acetic acid and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled at RT and then the suspension was poured into ice cold water. The product obtained was filtered, washed several times with cold water and purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol to give cream colour crystals. The compound was found homogeneous on TLC analysis using toluene : ethyl acetate (95 : 4) as solvent system. Other Schiff bases (**9b-j**) in this series were prepared in similar way. Yield 71% m.p. 252–254 °C, M.W. 695.70 (Found : C, 58.64, H, 4.25, N, 14.15. Calcd. for C₃₄H₂₉N₇O₈S : C, 58.70; H, 4.20; N, 14.09%).

*Synthesis of N1-{3-[(4-amino-5-sulfanyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)methyl]sulfanyl}-5-[2-(2,3-dimethoxy-5,12-dioxo-6,12-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4',5':5,6]indeno[1,2-c]isoquinolin-6-yl)ethyl]-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl}acetamide (**10**) :*

The **7** (1 mmol) was dissolved in alcoholic potassium hydroxide (1 mmol) and kept for stirring. Carbon disulphide (1.5 mmol) was added dropwise to this solution with stirring. Thick solid mass was obtained, to which 50 ml of absolute alcohol was added. Stirring was continued for 16 h. At the end of 16th h, dry ether was added to the mixture. The precipitate (thiocarbazate) obtained was taken immediately for the next step.

A solution of thiocarbazate (1 mmol) with hydrazine hydrate (1 mmol) was prepared in 10 ml ethanol and refluxed for 10–15 h with occasional shaking. The colour of the reaction mixture changed to light green with evolution of hydrogen sulfide gas. A homogenous mixture was obtained during the reaction process. The reaction mixture was cooled to RT and diluted with cold water (10 mL). On acidification with dil. HCl, the required triazole was precipitated as white precipitate. It was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and purified by recrystallization from DMSO. The compound was found homogeneous on TLC analysis using toluene : ethyl acetate : formic acid (5 : 4 : 1, v/v/v) as solvent system. Off white coloured solid obtained. Yield 48%, m.p. 228–230 °C, M.W. 663.68.

Anticancer activity by SRB assay method^{32,33} :

The antiproliferative SRB assay was performed to assess growth inhibition. This is a colorimetric assay which estimates cell number indirectly by staining total cellular protein with the SRB dye. The microtiter plates were taken out after 48 h incubation of the cells with test ma-

terials and gently layered with chilled 50% TCA in all the wells to produce a final concentration of 10%. The tissue culture plates were incubated at 4 °C for one hour to fix the cells attached to the bottom of the wells. The supernatant was then discarded. The plates were washed five times with distilled water to remove TCA, growth medium, low molecular weight metabolites, serum proteins etc. Plates were air dried and stored until further use. SRB solution was added to each well of the plates and incubated at room temperature for 30 min. The unbound SRB was removed quickly by washing the wells five times with 1% acetic acid and then air dried. 100 µL of Tris buffer (0.01 M, pH 10.4) was added and shaken gently for 5 min on a mechanical shaker. Optical density was recorded on ELISA reader at 515 nm.

DNA topoisomerase I assay^{34,35} :

The topoisomerase I inhibitory activity of the synthesized compounds was determined by a DNA relaxation assay on plasmid DNA of the recombinant *Leishmania* topoisomerase IB as per following procedure.

Plasmid DNA and enzyme : DNA used was negatively supercoiled pBluescript (SK+) isolated from *E. coli* host cells (DH5α) using standard purification protocol (Novagen).

Relaxation assay : DNA topoisomerase I was assayed by measuring the decreased mobility of the relaxed isomers of supercoiled pBluescript (SK+) DNA in an agarose gel. The standard topoisomerase assay mixture (25 µL) contained 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 5% glycerol, 50 mM KCl, 0.5 mM dithiothreitol (DTT), 10 mM MgCl₂, 30 µg/ml bovine serum albumin (BSA), 0.5 µg supercoiled DNA and 2 units of enzyme (1 unit is defined as the amount of DNA required to convert 50% of 0.5 µg supercoiled DNA substrate into the relaxed form under standard assay conditions) in absence and presence of varying drug concentrations. Reactions were performed at 37 °C for 30 min, and then terminated by adding 10 mM EDTA, 0.5% SDS, 0.25 µg/ml bromophenol blue and 15% (v/v) glycerol. The samples were electrophoresed in a horizontal 1% agarose gel in TAE buffer (40 mM tris/acetate, 2 mM EDTA, pH 8) at room temperature. The gels were stained with ethidium bromide (0.5 µg/ml), de-stained in water and photographed under UV illumination. Percentage relaxation was measured by microdensitometry of negative photographs of supercoiled monomer DNA band fluorescence after ethidium bromide staining.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, the anticancer screening of the novel series has demonstrated emergence of potent derivatives that have highly electronegative part at sulfhydryl group. While compound **2**, **5**, **7** and **9a** were found as a significant inhibitor for DNA-topoisomerase I. Since DNA topoisomerases are considered as important targets for cancer chemotherapy, the present findings may provide future opportunities to design and develop new chemotherapeutic agents.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful of Dr. A. S. Juvekar from Tata Memorial Centre, ACTREC, Mumbai for anticancer activity.

References

1. J. B. Gibbs, *Science*, 2000, **287**, 1969.
2. J. C. Wang, *Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1996, **65**, 635.
3. C. Y. Ting, C. T. Hsu, H. T. Hsu, J. S. Su, T. Y. Chen, W. Y. Tarn, Y. H. Kuo, W. P. Jacqueline, L. F. Liu and J. Hwang, *Biochem. Pharm.*, 2003, **66**, 1981.
4. L. Stewart, G. C. Ireton, L. H. Parker, K. R. Madden and J. J. Champoux, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1996, **271**, 7593.
5. Y. Pommier, P. Pourquier, Y. Fan and D. Strumberg, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1998, **1400**, 83.
6. Y. Pommier, *Nat. Rev. Cancer*, 2006, **6**, 789.
7. J. L. Nitiss, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1998, **1400**, 63.
8. L. Stewart, M. R. Redinbo, X. Qiu, W. G. J. Hol and J. J. Champoux, *Science*, 1998, **729**, 1534.
9. J. C. Wang, *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell. Biol.*, 2002, **3**, 430.
10. M. E. Wall, M. C. Wani, C. E. Cook, K. H. Palmer, A. T. McPhail and G. A. Sim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 3888.
11. J. O'Leary and F. M. Muggia, *Eur. J. Cancer*, 1998, **34**, 1500.
12. C. H. Takimoto, J. Wright and S. G. Arbuck, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1998, **1400**, 107.
13. M. Beran and H. Kantarjian, *Semin. Oncol.*, 1998, **35**, 26.
14. M. J. Luzzio, J. M. Besterman, D. L. Emerson, M. G. Evans, K. Lackey, P. L. Leitner, G. McIntyre, B. Morton, P. L. Myers, M. Peel, J. M. Sisco, D. D. Sternbach, W. Tong, A. Truesdale, D. E. Uehling, A. Vuong and J. Yates, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 395.
15. J. A. Gottlieb and J. K. Luce, *Cancer. Chemother. Rep.*, 1972, **56**, 103.
16. H. Minami, J. H. Beijnen, J. Verweij and M. J. Ratain, *Clin. Cancer Res.*, 1996, **2**, 43.
17. C. Jaxel, K. W. Kohn, M. C. Wani, M. E. Wall and Y. Pommier, *Cancer Res.*, 1989, **49**, 1465.
18. N. B. Haas, F. P. LaCreta, J. Walczak, G. R. Hudes, J. M. Brennan, R. F. Ozols and P. J. O'Dwyer, *Cancer Res.*, 1994, **54**, 1220.
19. G. Kohlhagen, K. D. Paull, M. Cushman, P. Nagafuji and Y. Pommier, *Mol. Pharm.*, 1998, **54**, 50.
20. M. Nagarajan, A. Morrell, B. C. Fort, M. R. Meckley, S. Antony, G. Kohlhagen, Y. Pommier and M. Cushman, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **47**, 5651.
21. A. Morrell, M. Placzek, S. Parmley, B. Grella, S. Antony, Y. Pommier and M. Cushman, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **50**, 4388.
22. A. Morrell, S. Antony, G. Kohlhagen, Y. Pommier and M. Cushman, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2004, **14**, 3659.
23. B. S. Holla, B. K. Sarojini, B. S. Rao, P. M. Akberali, N. S. Kumari and V. Shetty, *IL Farmaco.*, 2001, **56**, 565.
24. B. N. Goswami, J. C. S. Katakya and J. N. Baruah, *J Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1986, **23**, 1439.
25. K. S. Bhat, B. Poojary, D. J. Prasad, P. Naik and B. S. Holla, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 5066.
26. A. Yaseen, M. N. Al-Souda and N. A. Al-Dweria, *IL Farmaco.*, 2004, **59**, 775.
27. B. A. Baviskar, S. L. Deore, S. S. Khadabadi and M. R. Shiradkar, *Der Pharmacia Sinica*, 2012, **3**, 24.
28. M. R. Shiradkar, C. A. Kalyan, K. K. Murahari, H. G. Reddy, S. Tatikonda, A. K. Chakravarthy, D. Panchal, R. Kaur, P. Burange, J. Ghogare, V. Mokale and M. Raut, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 3997.
29. M. Shiradkar, J. Thomas, V. Kanase and R. Dighe, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 2066.
30. B. A. Baviskar, M. R. Shiradkar, S. S. Khadabadi, S. L. Deore and K. G. Bothara, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2011, **50**, 321.
31. M. R. Shiradkar, C. A. Kalyan, V. Dasari, V. Baru, B. Chiningiri, S. Gandhi and R. Kaur, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **15**, 2601.
32. P. Skehn, R. Storeng, A. Scudiero, J. Monks, D. McMohan, D. Vistica, T. W. Jonathan, H. Bokesch, S. Kenney and M. R. Boyd, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 1990, **82**, 1107.
33. P. Houghton, R. Fang, I. Techatanawat, G. Steventon, P. J. Hylands and C. C. Lee, *Nat. Prod. Res.*, 2007, **42**, 377.
34. A. Ganguly, B. B. Das, A. Roy, N. Sen, S. B. Dasgupta, S. Mukhopadhyay and H. K. Majumder, *Cancer Res.*, 2007, **67**, 11848.
35. P. Chaudhuri, H. K. Majumder and S. Bhattacharya, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **50**, 2536.